

MADRAS

D5.13 Communication Activities - 3

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Executive summary

The current deliverable details the communication activities that have been carried out from month 16 to month 30 including, among others:

- the blog posts created by each partner,
- the latest updates on the project website,
- current status of social media accounts and,
- production of the second, third and fourth project newsletters.

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List of abbreviations

<i>EUT</i>	<i>Eurecat</i>
<i>IME</i>	<i>In Mould Electronics</i>
<i>OLAE</i>	<i>Organic and Large Area Electronics</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>VCI</i>	<i>Visual Corporative Image</i>

Introduction

MADRAS is a 3-year research project that has the objective to demonstrate a materials-driven improvement of OLAE devices, developing a high-speed manufacturing methodology in a scalable competitive process, which is In Mould Electronics (IME).

The project also addresses the need for innovative and industrial manufacturing processes for the development of a robust series of plastronics products. Building on an already established technology as plastic injection will facilitate a faster up taking. In addition, the MADRAS project will validate new inks and printing methodology with two product demonstrators that will work as a fingerprint reader and a geo-tracking tag.

EUT is the partner leader of Task 5.7 Communication Activities, but all consortium partners are involved in it. Task 5.7 has the objective to create and provide all the communication materials needed for conveying the project to a broad group of users.

All the actions will consider the European Commission recommendations explained in the Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual section on project communication. (http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm).

Communication activities

1. Project's corporate visual identity image

At the beginning of the project, EUT developed MADRAS's **Visual Corporate Identity (VCI)**, aimed at properly aligning all communication materials across all the project's tasks. The VCI includes the project's logo, a Power Point template, Word document templates for project activities and a visual identity standards' guidebook, which defines and outlines how to use identifying elements pertaining to MADRAS.

See **D5.9 Visual Corporate Image** for more information and details of the Visual Corporate Identity designed and implemented.

Figure 1: MADRAS full colour logo

Stationery

Figure 2: View of some pages of the MADRAS Visual Corporate Image (VCI) manual

2. Public Website

The project website (www.madras-project.eu) was launched in June 2020 (M3), as defined in **Deliverable 5.10 - Public Project Website**, to serve as the main information platform for users interested in knowing more about MADRAS, displaying the project’s basic information, objectives, demonstrators and expected results.

Figure 3: Current MADRAS website structure

Following the plan established in previous deliverables, the website has been updated with a “Results” section, which includes the project’s outcomes and progress. Specifically, this

section contains the [page “Media”](#), which includes the project press release and a list of relevant articles featuring MADRAS. The [“Newsletters”](#) section includes the 3 project newsletters produced as of now and a banner to facilitate the subscription. The [“Promotional Materials”](#) section showcases the different promotional materials produced within the context of the project, which also comprise audio-visual content in the shape of videos. The [“Public deliverables”](#) section contains all the approved public deliverables, which are available for the website users to download and read. The confidential deliverables are also included in the section, however, the content included is limited to the executive summary. Finally, the “Results” section also includes a [“Scientific Publications”](#) page, created to include the scientific papers produced within the framework of MADRAS.

Additionally, the [“News & Events”](#) page has been updated with more news regarding the project, events in which partners had participated.

Regarding the blog posts, 13 new articles coming from all MADRAS partners have been published on the [“Blog”](#) website section since the last update on D5.12:

- [“Flexible thin-film fingerprint readers for integration into everyday products”](#) by TNO (July 1st, 2021): This article discusses the design of large-area flexible TFT backplanes on an ultra-thin polyimide plastic film, produced within the framework of MADRAS.
- [“Unlock the performance of Organic Photodetectors by “tuning” the PEDOT layers”](#) by the UPA (July 22nd, 2021): In this article, the theme treated is the opportunity that printed electronics serve to create functional structures and devices, using printable materials based mostly on organic photodetectors and materials.
- [“The starting point for in-mould organic photodetectors”](#) by EUT (August 31st, 2021): This post talks about the fabrication of an in-moulded fingerprint sensor with a fully printed organic photodetector’s (OPD) frontplane, which is one of the goals of the MADRAS project.
- [“Using LBIC as a tool for defect finding and surface analysis of photodetectors and solar cells”](#) by InfinityPV (November 9th, 2021): In this article, the author explains the development of a methodology for the injection moulding of organic thin film photodetectors as part of a fingerprint sensor, one of the MADRAS demonstrators.
- [“Development of a flexible battery-free geolocation tag based on advanced materials”](#) by UWINLOC (December 1st, 2021): This article describes UWINLOC’s role in the production process of the new flexible geotracking tag, one of the validation products of MADRAS.
- [“Standardisation activities to facilitate the commercialisation of the developed solutions in MADRAS”](#) by UNE (January 26th, 2022): UNE details in this blog post the existing related standards that have been used to develop MADRAS project in order to increase the visibility and impact of the project, as well as the performance of a report analysing the current standardisation landscape.
- [“Privacy by design in biometrics: why is it important for MADRAS?”](#) by Eticas (March 9th, 2022): In this post, the main topic is the description of the “privacy by design” concept and its application and importance for MADRAS. The author also reveals how is MADRAS ensuring and protecting users’ data in an ethic way thanks to a privacy by design culture.

- [“Optimising the transparency of Cellulose Nano Fibrils Films for more sustainable electronics’ manufacturing”](#) by AWCP (March 14th, 2022): Blog post explaining the MADRAS search for alternatives to plastic for a more sustainable-friendly manufacturing of electronic products. For that matter, AWCP has developed a high transparency CNF film made of cellulose, optimising it to up to a transparency of 90%.
- [“Developing advanced inks to replace the use of ITO in in-mould printing electronics”](#) by GNK (April 7th, 2022): This post reflects the efforts put in the development of a replacement for Indium Tin Oxide (ITO), a scarce and not very flexible material, in hybrid in-mould printed electronics.
- [“Making flimsy electronics reliable in everyday objects”](#) by TNO (May 31st, 2022): In this article, the topic discussed is the achievement the application of thin substrates with electronics on flat surfaces and thermoform these in the required shape, so-called in-mould electronics. This allows for much more freedom in prototyping, better scalability, and lower associated costs.
- [“Using fingerprint recognition for authentication in the vehicle sharing sector”](#) by eCooltra (July 8th, 2022). Blog post explaining the testing of a new fingerprint sensor prototype that, in connection with telematics and its back-end interface, will enable to activate the company’s scooters with the user’s fingerprint recognition.
- [“Designing the production of starting materials in reliable printing form for flexible substrates”](#) by COC (July 11th, 2022): This post focuses on the design of the production of starting materials in reliable printing form for flexible substrates.
- [“Analysing potential market sectors and use cases for MADRAS technology and materials”](#) by TNG (September 8th, 2022): This article presents a workshop carried out by MADRAS partners during a consortium meeting to identify the wide variety of markets in which MADRAS’ innovation can be applied.

See D5.10 Project Website for more details about blog posts information and guidelines prepared for all partners.

Figure 4: Examples of blog posts published on the website

Figure 5: Examples of posts published on social media sharing the two blog posts

Partners are contacted before their deadline and the topic is discussed together to avoid any overlapping between entities. All articles are edited by EUT and include a picture and short bio of the authors to give proper edit. To guide partners a blog post guideline with recommendations has been produced (see Annex 1).

For the last months of the project, the blog post calendar proposal will develop as the following:

PARTNER	Blog post 2
EUT	October 2022
INF	October 2022
ETR	November 2022
UWL	December 2022
ERC	December 2022
UNE	January 2023

Table 1: Blog post calendar

2.1 Analytics M1 - M30

The MADRAS website has Matomo tool installed on the platform's back end to monitor all the traffic and obtain, every month, reports about the site's performance.

Since its launch in M3 (June 2020), the website has received **2.586 visits**, **7.312 page visits** coming from **1.331 users** and **3,2 actions per visit** including **page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches** (analysis based on M3 - website creation until September 28th, 2022).

As for geographical and device traffic distribution, the majority of visits have come from Spain (denoting EUT's own efforts disseminating and communicating it at the Spanish level). The following figure seems relevant also to show that MADRAS has impacted beyond EU borders.

Figure 6: Top 5 visitor location per num. of visits and visitor map (Jun 2020 - Sept 2022)

Concerning devices, most of the sessions have been established through desktop devices. As shown in Figure 7, top viewed pages include the homepage, the page about MADRAS project, the section with information about OLAE and a page devoted to the project's demonstrators.

Figure 7: Top 5 most viewed pages and device types per visit

3. Promotional materials

EUT has produced and designed different types of promotional materials, including an **info-sheet**, **two rollup versions**, a **trifold**, a **factsheet template**, a **poster layout**, a **general presentation** and **different videos** focused on project's topics.

All the materials follow the MADRAS' VCI guidelines and are stored digitally in the project's internal repository, as well as on the project's website for broader dissemination. Users can download them in the "[Promotional Materials](#)" section on the website.

Figure 8: Promotional materials published on the project's website

A factsheet template has been created with the objective to share all relevant MADRAS' deliverables on project's website and also through the Zenodo Community in order to show results and impacts achieved by the project.

The info-sheet template will be used to share the following project's deliverables, once submitted and validated:

- D1.4 - Optimised nanocellulose foil - 2
- D1.5 - Optimised organic conducting inks - 2
- D1.6 - Optimised inorganic semiconducting inks - 2
- D2.3 - Printed materials and devices - 2
- D2.4 - Development of IME and thermoforming - 2
- D3.2 - Geo-tracking flexible tag
- D3.3 - Biometric photosensor
- D4.4 - Implementation of the industrialisation of IME

ADVANCED MATERIALS AND
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Factsheet - DATE dd/mm/yyyy

Poster title: Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Introduction / Executive summary

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HIGHLIGHTED SENTENCE:
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www.madras-project.eu

@MADRAS_Project

info@madras-project.eu

 The project has received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 862492

Figure 9: Deliverables' factsheet template

4. Audio-visual materials

Engaging audio-visual materials (e.g., videos) have been produced to present the key aspects of the project. The videos produced within the project are published on the MADRAS website, the YouTube channel and promoted on all project channels (social media).

4.1 Videos produced (M16-M30)

At M19 (September 2021), a video recording was published about the presentation of the project by MADRAS partners from Tecnopackaging during a session held within the 9th Annual World Congress of Advanced Materials (WCAM), which took place from August 26th - 28th.

See the video [here](#).

Figure 10: View of the video recording shared on the MADRAS YouTube channel

At M21 (November 2021), a video was produced by UWL, explaining one of the project demonstrators: a flexible battery-free geolocation tag based on advanced materials. It contains closed captioning in English.

The important innovation of the demo is achieved by means of a specific production process. It goes from the choice of the material based on nanocellulose foil, the printing process and the hybridisation techniques.

See the video [here](#).

Figure 11: View of the video produced and shared on the MADRAS YouTube channel

At M28 (July 2022), an animated video of the MADRAS project was produced by EUT. This video with motion graphics describes the project main objectives and expected outputs. It contains closed captioning in English.

See the video [here](#).

Figure 12: View of the animated video produced and shared on the YouTube channel

At M28 (July 2022), EUT published a video interview with Benjamin Dhuiege, Head of R&D from Genesink, detailing the development and properties of two types of inks: a transparent conductive ink based on silver nanowires and a semiconductive ink based on hybrid WO_3 nanoparticles.

See the video [here](#).

Figure 13: View of the interview produced and shared on the MADRAS YouTube channel

In the same month (M28), EUT published another video interview, this time with Gael Depres, Central R&D Manager from Arjowiggins. He explains the development of a translucent and conductive paper for an increased transparency, serving as a replacement to plastique films, in order to reduce the environmental project of the demonstrators.

See the video [here](#).

All these videos have been shared through MADRAS' Twitter and LinkedIn accounts and published in the project's YouTube channel.

4.2 Videos to be produced (M31-M36)

The proposed videos to be produced on the last months of the project are:

- **M34-M36 - Production process MADRAS demonstrators:** Video of the production process of each of the products validated with MADRAS technology. Partners will be in charge of recording images during the products' production in their facilities.
- **M34-M36 - Experiments, production processes:** short videos produced by partners conducting MADRAS tests / experiments, production processes for social media.

5. Social Media

EUT is managing MADRAS' social media accounts, including a Twitter profile ([@MADRAS_Project](#)) created at M1, a [YouTube channel](#) created at M4 and a [LinkedIn account](#) created at M14 (May 2021).

Partners are contributing to spread the word through their corporate and personal Social Media channels, including Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram.

5.1 Twitter

MADRAS' Twitter account is managed by EUT with the support of project partners for the correct management of the profile.

The project's main objective on Twitter is to raise awareness on flexible electronics, OLAE devices production processes, benefits and new materials allowing the development of devices by printing techniques with increased robustness, while reducing their cost and environmental impact, as well as promoting the project's methodology / industrial production process to key stakeholders and the broader audience.

Figure 14: MADRAS Twitter Profile

5.1.1 Analytics (M16 - M30)

A profile in Twitter Analytics has been activated in order to measure Twitter's and other data about the account activity. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

MADRAS activity on Twitter is being tracked monthly by EUT. The following table shows the account performance up to M30 (September 2022). In September 2022, the MADRAS Twitter account counts with **148 followers** and has generated **342 tweets** and more than **80K impressions**.

MADRAS Twitter account	M1-M30
Followers	148
Total tweets	342
Twitter impressions	80.041
Mentions	45

Likes on tweets	472
Retweets	193

Table 2: MADRAS Twitter profile data (M1-M30)

Figure 15: View of Twitter Analytics panel

5.1.2 Strategy

At the beginning of the project, EUT has detailed a Social Media strategy to follow, which mixes marketing content, branding and influence actions in order to maximise MADRAS' project impact and facilitate market uptake.

The different posts published include content curation with news and information related to project's topics, events in which partners have participated, dissemination of consortium meetings, promotion of the newsletter sign-up form created, distribution of the promotional materials and the press release produced, and other news related to MADRAS, among others.

Deliverable 5.11 **MADRAS Communication Activities** explains and details the Social Media strategy and management policy.

MADRAS project @MADRAS_Project · 2 ago. ...
 Have you watched our heads-up with Benjamin Dhuiege, Head of R+D from @genesink?

He explains the development of 2 types of #inks within #MADRAS: a conductive ink based on silver nanowires and a semiconductive ink based on hybrid #WO3 nanoparticles 🙌

[Traducir Tweet](#)

youtube.com
 MADRAS - Conductive and semiconductive inks: t...
 In this video, Benjamin Dhuiege, Head of R&D from Genesink, details the development and properties ...

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MADRAS project @MADRAS_Project · 11 jul. ...
 One of the #MADRAS project demonstrators is a biometric reader based on #photodetection 🙌

In our latest blog post, @Cooltra explains how the use of the #fingerprint for user's authentication can be the guarantee of maximum security for their scooters 🚲

[Traducir Tweet](#)

madras-project.eu
 Using fingerprint recognition for authentication in the vehicle sharing s...
 Using fingerprint recognition for authentication in the vehicle sharing sector

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MADRAS project @MADRAS_Project · 19 jul. ...
 A #MADRAS scientific paper has been presented in the @IEEEorg AP/S-URSI Conference, an international forum on state-of-the-art research in #antennas 📡

🙌 The paper has been contributed by different project partners and presented by @Uwinloc

Full story:
[Traducir Tweet](#)

International Symposium on Antennas & Propagation
SNC-URSI
Radio Science Meeting
0-15, 2022 • DENVER

madras-project.eu
 MADRAS paper presented during the AP-S/URSI 2022 Conference - ...
 A scientific paper related to MADRAS project research has been presented in the IEEE International Symposium on Antennas & ...

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MADRAS project @MADRAS_Project · 29 jun. ...
 Join #MADRAS community of interest!

📧 Receive in your inbox the latest news on our #AdvancedMaterials for the mass production of #OLAE #PrintedElectronics products

cutt.ly/MADRASNewslett...

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ADVANCED MATERIALS AND PROCESSING IN ORGANIC ELECTRONICS
Subscribe to MADRAS newsletter!
 Join our community and be updated on project progress & results
www.madras-project.eu

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Figure 16: Examples of tweets published on MADRAS Twitter profile

5.2 YouTube

The YouTube account was created in M4 (July 2021). [MADRAS YouTube Channel](#) has been used as a video content repository and its content links have been shared on social media and through MADRAS' website.

For the moment, the channel has **6 videos published**. At M30, MADRAS YouTube Channel has achieved more than **1371 visualisations** and **22 subscribers**.

Figure 17: MADRAS YouTube profile

5.3 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a platform for the interaction among professionals to exchange experiences to improve their work placement. The channel allows users to create interesting groups around specific initiatives or projects, ask or answer questions, post or search for jobs, etc.

EUT created a [MADRAS LinkedIn page](#) on M14 (May 2021), which allows to connect the academic and industrial community. The content published on LinkedIn is very similar to Twitter publications and is based on project news, blog posts, achievements, events attended by partners, newsletters and reports or publications produced in the framework of the project.

Figure 18: MADRAS LinkedIn profile

Figure 19: Examples of posts published on LinkedIn MADRAS account

The LinkedIn account is being managed by EUT with the collaboration of all project’s partners, who can propose contents to be distributed through this channel. Partners are welcomed to spread the word through their own corporate and personal channels by sharing the content published.

Contents published on MADRAS LinkedIn include:

- Blog posts produced and published on project’s website
- Partners participation in key events, fairs and congresses on project topics
- News and achievements related to the project and published in MADRAS website
- Audio-visual and digital promotional materials
- Press releases
- Specific information related to the project’s topics that can be interesting to the industrial and academic community.

Publishing, as well as comments, answers and private messages are managed manually in order to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

The use of hashtags is highly recommended (the same as defined in the Twitter strategy in Deliverable 5.11 MADRAS Communication Activities).

Data on publications' impact is being retrieved periodically from LinkedIn Analytics. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

MADRAS LinkedIn profile	M1-M30
Followers	106
Total posts	72
Likes & reactions	470
Shares	120
Impressions	18.150

Table 3: MADRAS LinkedIn profile data at month 30

5.4 Partners channels

Each partner transmits MADRAS news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram), including press releases, news about events, promotional materials and other contents published previously on www.madras-project.eu or in MADRAS' Twitter account.

At M30, partners have published 36 posts on social media, accounting for 240 likes and reactions and 38 retweets / shares.

Figure 20: Examples of partners' posts about MADRAS published on partners' accounts

6. Media relations

A press release with general information about the project and its consortium was produced, which was distributed to all partners and adapted to several languages.

EUT has written this first press release with the inputs of all the project's partners, which have validated all the content before sending it to the media outlets.

The press release produced had an important impact on online and print media. As a result, MADRAS project has been featured in **10 Spanish and English media outlets at regional, national, and international level**, including OAE-OPE Journal, Printed Electronics World, La Razón, MundoPlast or Interempresas, among others. See Annex 2 for a complete list of articles featuring MADRAS.

- Consortium press release: [European consortium to test new materials and manufacturing processes for organic printed electronics](#)

Figure 21: Press release published on MADRAS website. See the full text [here](#)

Additionally, some partners adapted and published the consortium press release in their corporate webpages. See a complete list of these publications at Section 5 of D5.15 MADRAS Communication Materials.

On May 2022 (M26), MADRAS was featured in [Consumer Electronic Test and Development magazine](#). This is a specialised media, focusing on case studies, in-depth reports, technological insights, development and testing of consumer electronic products around the world and include selected research in the magazine. An [article](#) on the developments carried out with the Madras project was published providing an overview of the objectives of the project, and materials developed. Moreover, the editors have expressed their interest on publishing a new article once the demonstrators are finalised.

Figure 22: Article published on Consumer Electronics Magazine website

6.1 Press release plan

For the following months, the press releases calendar envisioned is the following:

MADRAS press release plan		Partner responsible
M32	Novel materials developed	EUT, AWCP, GNK, COC, UPA
M34	Geo-tracking flexible tag	EUT, UWL
M35	Biometric Photosensor	EUT, ERC
M36	Final press release project results	EUT

Table 4: Press release plan proposal

7. Newsletters

At M30 (September 2022), EUT as MADRAS Communication Leader has produced and sent 4 **project's newsletters**, including different information about the project, its progress and achievements.

- MADRAS 1st Newsletter (M15): information about the project's main objectives and expected results, our participation in the 5E Digital Showcase, In-mould integration of printed flexible photodetectors, the latest blog posts published and a selection of media articles featuring MADRAS.
<https://mailchi.mp/0b3cc8289415/madras-project-newsletter-the-latest-updates-on-advanced-inks-and-organic-printed-electronics-research>
- MADRAS 2nd Newsletter (M19): information about the project's demonstrators, a selection of articles based on the latest project updates, new MADRAS dissemination and promotional materials developed and the latest dissemination activities and events attended by project's partners
<https://mailchi.mp/b4ee03e65b99/madras-project-newsletter-the-latest-updates-on-advanced-inks-and-organic-printed-electronics-research-9816861>
- MADRAS 3rd Newsletter (M25): content about Organic and Large Area Electronics (OLAE), access to MADRAS public deliverables, the latest dissemination activities and events attended by project's partners and other interesting topics about the project.
<https://mailchi.mp/94e312d5e8d8/madras-project-newsletter-the-latest-updates-on-advanced-inks-and-organic-printed-electronics-research-11453218>
- MADRAS 4th Newsletter (M30): it includes the latest blog post published by MADRAS, the latest videos produced within the project or the most recent dissemination activities.
<https://mailchi.mp/acff0deefc1c/madras-project-newsletter-the-latest-updates-on-advanced-inks-and-organic-printed-electronics-research-12131000?e=bd94be67c7>

Hello!

Welcome to the first newsletter of the [MADRAS project](#).

We took off in April 2020 with the aim to develop new materials and manufacturing processes for scalable mass production of organic electronics devices, also known as OLAE devices, integrated into plastic parts for accelerated time-to-market.

In this issue, you will be able to find about:

- What is MADRAS Horizon 2020 project, main objectives and expected results.
- MADRAS participation in the 5E project Digital Showcase
- In-mould integration of printed flexible photodetectors
- The latest articles on the development of advanced inks and printing materials for organic electronic devices
- A selection of media articles featuring MADRAS

We hope you enjoy reading our newsletter and invite you to check our website regularly, follow us on social media or contact us directly for more information at info@madras-project.eu.

MADRAS at a quick glance!

The [MADRAS project](#) is developing low cost and reliable materials for a high-volume production of flexible plastronic products.

The project has the objective to boost the production of Organic and Large-Area Electronics (OLAE) by establishing a high-speed manufacturing methodology based on In-Mould Electronics (IME) optimised with improved materials and inks.

MADRAS takes part in 5E project Digital Showcase!

MADRAS has joined the [5E project Digital Showcase](#), an online platform aiming at increasing visibility and new opportunities for European electronics products, specifically whose innovative character builds on the combination of Nano-Electronics, Flexible, Organic & Printed Electronics and Electronic Smart Systems. The platform also includes products based on novel technologies and tools developed in the context of funded projects at a regional, national or EU level.

[Find out more](#)

MADRAS in the news!

See below a brief selection of articles featuring MADRAS:

- [Nano inks with novel functionalities](#) - OAE, OPE Journal (November 2020)
- [European consortium test new materials for organic printed electronics](#) - Printed Electronics World (November 2020)
- [Dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos, la alternativa al cobre y al silicio](#) (in Spanish) - La Razón (October 2020)
- [Eurecat investiga nuevos materiales para plastrónica](#) (in Spanish) - Mundoplast.com (October 2020)
- [Ensayan nuevos materiales y procesos de fabricación de dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos](#) (in Spanish) - Interempresas (October 2020)

About MADRAS project

MADRAS is a European project funded under H2020 grant agreement No. 862492 developing new materials and manufacturing processes for a scalable

Figure 22: View of some sections of the first newsletter published

Hello!

Welcome to the second newsletter of **MADRAS project**, aimed at developing **new materials and manufacturing processes for scalable mass production of organic electronics devices**, also known as OLAE devices, integrated into plastic parts for accelerated time-to-market.

In this issue, you will be able to find more about:

- **MADRAS project demonstrators**
- **A selection of articles based on the latest project updates**
- **New MADRAS dissemination and promotional materials developed**
- **The latest dissemination activities and events attended by project's partners**

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Latest project updates

Flexible thin-film fingerprint readers for integration into everyday products

The **MADRAS project** is developing a highly secure, high resolution, mechanically stable **fingerprint readers** for user authentication that will be integrated into the hard plastics of scooters.

Find out how **TNO-Holst Centre** designs and builds large-area flexible TFT backplanes on a ultra-thin polyimide plastic film and evaluates the thin-film encapsulation (TFE) stack, consisting of two inorganic barrier layers of silicon nitride deposited at low temperature with an organic layer in between.

[MORE INFORMATION](#)

MADRAS demonstrators

MADRAS project demonstrates and validates its novel production methodology and materials in **two different demonstrators**, including a **biometric photosensor** for fingerprint user's recognition of a scooter-sharing company and a **geotracking flexible tag** for the packaging and logistics sector.

The products reflect not only large market potential applications of flexible and wearable electronics, but also demonstrate the unique **MADRAS technology approach** based on applying advanced materials and soft fabrication techniques in the development of **OLAE devices**.

A geotracking flexible tag

Development of a flexible tag to be attached to objects such as tools, vehicles and parts in assembly lines compatible with curved surfaces for their geolocalisation in **UWINLOC** facilities.

An important innovation of the demo is the **implementation of an RF energy harvesting system** through its antenna that will enable a battery free tag.

In MADRAS project, **the new smart tag will be prepared as a flexible self-adhesive label with a rigid electronic unit** with optimised power energy management and enhanced geolocalisation features.

MADRAS promotional materials

Learn more about advanced materials and processing in organic electronics with our new promotional materials

The main results of the MADRAS project have been summarised in a **library of promotional and informational materials** that can be used for any communication activity or dissemination event.

The list of materials available include a **brochure, an infosheet, two rollups and a general presentation** offering an overview about the project, its main objectives, the expected results, the demonstrators to be developed and more.

[DOWNLOAD THEM](#)

Figure 23: View of some sections of the second newsletter published

Hello!

Welcome to the third newsletter of the [MADRAS project](#), aimed at developing **new materials and manufacturing processes for a scalable mass production of organic electronics devices**, also known as OLAE devices, integrated into plastic parts for accelerated time-to-market.

In this issue, you will be able to find more about:

- OLAE, the new dimension of electronics
- LBIC as a tool for defect finding and surface analysis of photodetectors and solar cells
- Development of a flexible battery-free geolocation tag based on advanced materials
- Standardisation activities to facilitate the commercialisation of the developed solutions in MADRAS
- Privacy by design in biometrics and its importance for MADRAS
- Optimisation of the transparency of Cellulose Nano Fibrils Films for more sustainable electronics' manufacturing
- Access to MADRAS latest public deliverables
- The latest dissemination activities and events attended by project's partners

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Latest project updates

Using LBIC as a tool for defect finding and surface analysis of photodetectors and solar cells

[MADRAS project](#) is developing a scalable methodology to minimise the thermal effects of injection moulding of organic thin film photodetectors as a part of a [fingerprint sensor](#), which is one of the demonstrators.

Find out how [InfinityPV](#) is implementing Light Beam Induced Current, as known as LBIC, an ultrafast technique that gives an image of a device with each pixel in the picture representing how well a photodetector works in a matter of seconds-to-minutes, depending on the size of the photodetector.

[MORE INFORMATION](#)

[MORE PUBLIC DELIVERABLES](#)

MADRAS dissemination activities

Partners from UWINLOC and GenesInk disseminate MADRAS at LOPEC 2022

MADRAS partners from [UWINLOC](#) and from [GenesInk](#) have recently disseminated the project in [LOPEC 2022](#), the main event in Europe concerning printed electronics.

[READ MORE](#)

More events in which MADRAS was present:

[MADRAS takes part in Advanced Factories 2022](#). March 2022. [READ MORE](#)

[Eurecat presents MADRAS in the online forum EF ECS 2021](#). February 2022. [READ MORE](#)

[Genesink pitches MADRAS to potential investors](#). January 2022. [READ MORE](#)

[UWINLOC presents MADRAS during the GITEX 2021 Exhibition](#). October 2021. [READ MORE](#)

[UWINLOC partners bring MADRAS project to a SIDO Lyon Conference](#). September 2021. [READ MORE](#)

[AGENDA AND MORE PAST EVENTS HERE](#)

Figure 24: View of some sections of the third newsletter published

Hello!

Welcome to the fourth newsletter of **MADRAS project**, aimed at developing **new materials and manufacturing processes for scalable mass production of organic electronics devices**, also known as OLAE devices, integrated into plastic parts for accelerated time-to-market.

In this issue, you will be able to find more about:

- The development of advanced inks to replace the use of ITO in in-mould printing electronics
- Making flimsy electronics reliable in everyday objects
- The use of fingerprint recognition for authentication in the vehicle sharing sector
- The design of the production of starting materials in reliable printing form for flexible substrates
- Analysing potential market sectors and use cases for MADRAS technology and materials
- The celebration of the latest MADRAS Project Board in Barcelona
- The latest videos of the MADRAS project
- The latest dissemination activities and events attended by project's partners

We hope you enjoy reading our newsletter and invite you to check our website regularly, follow us on social media or contact us directly for more information at info@madras-project.eu.

Latest project updates

Developing advanced inks to replace the use of ITO in in-mould printing electronics

In MADRAS, **GenesInk** is leading the advance of materials performance by developing advanced inks that will be implemented as Transparent Conductive Electrodes (TCE).

These new materials are meant to be the European alternative for ITO in flexible and hybrid in-mould printed electronics, allowing the development of devices by printing techniques with increased robustness, while reducing their cost and environmental impact.

[MORE INFORMATION](#)

Making flimsy electronics reliable in everyday objects

The in-mould biometric sensor under development in MADRAS consists of an organic photodiode (OPD) frontplane on top of an IGZO-TFT backplane.

To finalise the device and protect it mechanically, as well as from degradation by moisture in the ambient, a thin film encapsulation is applied. This device will be thermoformed into the desired shape and over-moulded for its integration into the body of a scooter.

[MORE INFORMATION](#)

MADRAS animated video

Have a look at the interviews with some of our partners

Translucent and conductive cellulose-based paper and its application in the project

Conductive and semiconductive inks: the alternative for ITO in flexible printed electronics

MADRAS latest dissemination activities

MADRAS paper presented during the AP-S/URSI 2022 Conference. July 2022. [READ MORE](#)

Eurecat presents MADRAS in FLEPS 2022. July 2022. [READ MORE](#)

Arjowiggins disseminates MADRAS in a round table about plastronics. April 2022. [READ MORE](#)

[AGENDA AND MORE PAST EVENTS HERE](#)

Figure 25: View of some sections of the fourth newsletter published

The MADRAS newsletters are being disseminated via links on social media, direct *ad hoc* emails to professional contacts of the consortium partners and via browsing the MADRAS website, where all produced newsletter issues are stored.

See Section 6 at D5.11 MADRAS Communication activities for more information and details regarding newsletters management, platform, content, etc.

PROJECT NEWSLETTERS

Newsletter 1 - June 2021

In the first newsletter of MADRAS project you can find more information about the project's main objectives and expected results, our participation in the 5E Digital Showcase, in-mould integration of printed flexible photodetectors, the latest blog posts published and a selection of media articles featuring MADRAS.

[Read the newsletter](#)

Newsletter 2 - October 2021

This is the second newsletter of MADRAS project in which you can find more information about the project's demonstrators, a selection of articles based on the latest project updates, new MADRAS dissemination and promotional materials developed and the latest dissemination activities and events attended by project's partners.

[Read the newsletter](#)

Newsletter 3 - April 2022

This is the third newsletter of MADRAS project in which you can find more information about Organic and Large Area Electronics (OLAE), access to MADRAS public deliverables, the latest dissemination activities and events attended by project's partners and other interesting topics about the project.

[Read the newsletter](#)

Figure 26: MADRAS Project Newsletters page

Figure 27: Examples of posts published on social media sharing the project’s newsletter

Newsletter analytics, such as open rate or click through rate, are **extracted through Mailchimp platform**. Statistics are being checked 3 days after sending the newsletter and are analysed in order to see which articles worked best so we can improve the newsletter impact in the following issues.

The following table includes data regarding the first three project’s newsletters. The fourth newsletter statistics have not been considered for this analysis as it has been sent hours before the submission of this deliverable.

These newsletters have been sent to an audience up to 56 subscribers.

MADRAS 1 st -3 rd Newsletters	
Open rate	32,4%
Total opens	119
Clicks through rate	13,7%
Clicks per unique opens	41,7%
Total clicks	45
Successful deliveries	95%

Table 5: MADRAS 1st-3rd newsletter analytics

The last two newsletters of the project will be produced and shared following this schedule:

MADRAS Newsletters	Month
5th newsletter	M33
6th newsletter	M36

Table 6: MADRAS newsletters calendar

8. Partners communication activities

From M16-30 of the project, partners have also done diverse types of communication actions in order to increase awareness about the project and disseminate it through a large audience. Some of these activities are the inclusion of the project's information on their corporate website and newsletters, publication of MADRAS's news on their social media channels, or the production of some promotional materials, among others.

Date	Partner	Type of dissemination action	Description	Type of audience	Link
July 2021	EUT	Newsletter	Inclusion of information about a MADRAS presentation into EUT internal newsletter sent to all employees	Scientific & Academic Community	N/A
September 2021	TNG	Video-visual/audio-visual material	Video recording of the presentation of MADRAS during the World Congress of Advanced Materials	Scientific & Academic Community	Link
November 2021	EUT	Newsletter	Inclusion of the second MADRAS newsletter into EUT internal newsletter sent to all employees	Scientific & Academic Community	N/A
November 2021	UWL	Video-visual/audio-visual material	Flexible geotracking tag video	General public	Link
April 2022	EUT	Newsletter	Inclusion of the third MADRAS newsletter into EUT internal newsletter sent to all employees	Scientific & Academic Community	N/A
May 2022	EUT	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	Article in "Consumer Electronics - Test & Development" magazine with an overview of the project	General public	Link
June 2022	EUT	Newsletter	Inclusion of information about a MADRAS consortium meeting into EUT internal newsletter sent to all employees	Scientific & Academic Community	N/A
July 2022	EUT	Newsletter	Inclusion the MADRAS animated video into EUT internal newsletter sent to all employees	Scientific & Academic Community	N/A

July 2022	EUT	Video-visual/audio-visual material	Project animated video	General public	Link
July 2022	EUT	Video-visual/audio-visual material	Video interview with Benjamin Dhuiège, from GenesInk	General public	Link
July 2022	EUT	Video-visual/audio-visual material	Video interview with Gael Depres, from Arjowiggins	General public	Link

Table 7: List of partners' communication activities (M1-M15)

Communication activities management

9. Communication KPIs

The following table introduces an initial set of MADRAS Key performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessing the communication activities. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	M1-M30	Target by the end of the project
Media	Number of press releases	Proof of publication and reporting in reports / project meetings	1	>2
	Number of articles published		12	>30
Website	Number of web visits	Matomo Analytics	2,586	>4,000
	Number Pages Viewed		7,312	>10,000
	Number page / session		3.2	>1,5
	Number users		1,331	>2,000
	Avg. session time		4,33 min	>3,00 min (70% of the users)
Newsletters	Number of newsletters issued	Proof of publication in reports	4	6

Social Media - Twitter	Number Followers	Twitter Analytics	148	>200
	Number Tweets		342	>150
	Twitter Impressions		80,041	>50,000
	Number mentions		45	>20
Social Media - YouTube	Number of videos uploaded	Proof of publication in reports	6	>2
Social Media - LinkedIn	Number Followers	LinkedIn Analytics	106	>50
	Number Posts		72	>50
	Likes / Reactions		470	>100
Social Media - Partners	Number of posts in corporate channels	Monthly follow up (quantitative)	36	>20
	Number of Likes in corporate channels		240	>50
	Number Shares / Retweets in corporate channels		36	>10
	Participation in LinkedIn groups		0	Proof of publication

Table 8: Communication KPIs (M1-M30)

9.1 Communication Activities Calendar

COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES MADRAS	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
	oct-22	nov-22	dec-22	jan-23	feb-23	mar-23
Update Twitter Account	X	X	X	X	X	X
Website update	X	X	X	X	X	X
Video interviews to partners for social media				X	X	X
Videos on production process MADRAS demonstrators				X	X	X
Videos on MADRAS experiments and production process				X	X	X
Press release materials developed		X				
Project info sheets based on deliverables' results	X	X	X	X	X	X
5th Newsletter			X			
Press Release Business Case eCooltra					X	
Press Release Business Case UWINLOC				X		
Press Release end of the project - results						X
6th Newsletter						X
D5.14 Communication Activities Report Update						X

ANNEX

1. Media clipping (M16-M30)

Date	Media	Title	Typology	Link
18/05/22	Consumer Electronics	A future built from 'organic' electronics	Online	Link

Table 9: List of articles featuring MADRAS published in media outlets